

The Roman courtesan Julia da Gallese (1529–1565); her life and fortune

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This is the story of Julia, born in 1529 in the village of Gallese, and brought to Rome by her mother when she was small. At the age of 14 years Julia was engaged to marry Orazio Alidosi, but if she actually married, her husband almost immediately disappeared. The year after, now aged 15 years, Julia became a courtesan. She never achieved fame or notoriety during her lifetime, but some of her personal papers have survived. Though they deal mainly with her finances there is enough material to reconstruct the vivid outlines of her life. These papers are now in the archive of the Biblioteca Corsiniana in Rome, in the collection entitled *Pia Casa degli orfani di Santa Maria in Aquiro*, with the press-mark SMA.¹ Thus, references in the following essay such as SMA 152.20 should be read as tome 152, folio 20.

1. Kolega 2015

The village where Julia was born, Gallese, is about 50 km north of Rome, and a few kilometres from the River Tiber. With its maze of narrow alleys the village remains little altered from Julia's day, mainly due to its peculiar isolation. The only changes that a visitor from the past might note are that the houses have been modernized, and their inhabitants are in peculiar, modern dress. The village population is now about 2000, probably much the same as in the sixteenth century.

Although Rome was then a forge of European cultural history Julia, on arrival, would have probably have seen only a city dissolute, violent and rich, with the riches almost entirely in the hands of the cardinals and nobles. It would have seemed huge, even if it had but 60 000 inhabitants. In common with Gallese were the filthy, muddy, unpaved streets. As for her prospects, there were few. The great majority of girls like her were destined to be wives, or servants. Julia's mother Francesca decided that it would be the former. Julia's father, Roberto Tagliacozzo, is not mentioned at this point and was presumably already dead.

Julia was to marry Orazio de Alidosi, a widower with two small sons.² The Alidosi were a noble family from Imola, but Orazio Alidosi despite his nobility, was evidently far from rich. Another member of the family, Ottavio Alidosi (†1546), was the trusted domestic servant (*cubicularius*) of pope Paolo III (i.e. Alessandro Farnese the elder), and a member of the household (*famigliare*) of Cardinal Alessandro Farnese the younger.³ It may be inferred

2. SMA 26.1r

3. Forcella 1869,
vol. 1, n° 1308

that Julia's mother Francesca also had some connection with the cardinal's household.

The dowry that Orazio was evidently content with was a modest 150 scudi. Of this, Julia's mother had already paid 25 scudi, but needed six months to pay the rest. To appreciate the size of the dowry it may be recalled that in 1564 poor girls from deprived backgrounds, daughters of *Cortegiane, ò Donne di mala vita, e persone d'estrema povertà* who were educated in the newly completed convent of Santa Caterina de' Funari, in Rome, were provided with dowries of about 60 scudi.¹ A little later, Cardinal Alessandro Farnese the younger in his testament of 1587 left 19 scudi as a dowry for each of three '*vergini povere miserabili*'.² These data make Julia's dowry of 150 scudi seem quite respectable. However, noblewomen at this time would have had dowries of at least 1000 scudi.³

1. Piazza 1698, p. 182

2. Rosini 2005, p. 68

3. Calcaterra 2004, pp. 142–146

The scudo was a tiny gold coin weighing slightly over 3 g, divided into 10 juli and 100 baiocchi, and with a present-day bullion value of about 150 euro.

The date of the marriage with Orazio Alidosi is uncertain, for only an undated extract from the marriage contract survives. It was probably in 1543, when Julia reached the age of 14 years and would be generally regarded as marriageable. The marriage, however, must have come to a swift end, for Orazio Alidosi never appears subsequently in Julia's life.

On reaching 15 years in 1544 Julia changed her plans, perhaps having discovered that for her, marriage was equivalent to being an unpaid domestic servant and concubine. Furthermore, if her husband had died Julia would have found that she would get her dowry back, but no more; her husband's wealth, such as it was, would have been inherited by his sons. So Julia decided, perhaps persuaded by her mother, to become a courtesan, i.e. a superior kind of prostitute. It is to be hoped that Julia's mother explained to her the reality of prostitution. Veronica Franco (1546–1591), a Venetian courtesan celebrated for her poetry, and with long experience of the profession, wrote a letter to the mother of a girl contemplating the career pointing out its horrors – though carefully failing to mention the rosy prospect of financial independence;

darsi in preda di tanti, con rischio d'esser dispogliata, d'esser rubbata, d'esser uccisa; ch'un solo un dì ti toglia quanto con molti in molto tempo hai acquistato con tant'altri pericoli d'ingiurie, & d'infermità contagiose, & spaventose? mangiar con l'altrui bocca, dormir con gli occhi altrui, muoversi secondo l'altrui desiderio, correndo in manifesto naufragio sempre della facoltà, & della vita, qual maggior miseria? quai ricchezze, quai commodità, quai delitiae posson acquistar un tanto peso? Credete a me, tra tutte le sciagure mondane questa è l'estrema; ma poi se s'aggiungeranno à i rispetti del mondo quei dell'anima, che perdizione, & che certezza di dannatione è questa?⁴

4. Franco 1580, pp. 44–45; cf. Masson 1975, p. 165

to make yourself the prey of many, with risk of being stripped of everything, robbed, murdered; in a day, to lose everything gained over many years through such risky labours, not to mention catching contagious and horrible illnesses? Eat with the mouth of someone else, sleep with the eyes of someone else, move at the whim of someone else, racing towards the obvious destruction of your mind, and life, what greater misery could there be? What wealth, what convenience, what delight can be had at such a price? Believe me, among all the misfortunes of the world and the soul, this is the worst; to which you have to add the certainty of eternal damnation.

If Julia was thus warned it had not the desired effect; she went ahead anyway. She rented a house in an area which, in 1549, was described as *Da Francia*. This was near the then French embassy, close to the present Piazza di Spagna.¹ It was a financially attractive location for courtesans, for sixteen others lived close by. In consequence of having a house at her disposal Julia attracted the attention of the Bargello di Corte Savella (the criminal court dealing with papal dependants), and found herself listed as a courtesan – something she would have doubtless preferred to have avoided, since it rendered her liable to non-recurrent (i.e. one-off) taxation.

1. Mendoza, pp. 141 & 241

Julia's mother, Francesca, who may have been a financially unsuccessful courtesan, stayed with her in her new home. The suggestion that Julia's mother was a courtesan is not at all unlikely for there are numerous instances of mothers and daughters succeeding each other in this field, both in the 1549 tax roll and in the literature of the period – one could cite, for example, the much celebrated courtesans Veronica Franco and Tullia d'Aragona, both introduced to the profession by their mothers. Francesca could well be the *Francischa cortesana* in Campo Marzio in 1527.² The 1527 census of Rome was prepared on the eve of the sack of Rome, after which most of the surviving inhabitants of the city deserted it. Francesca probably went back to Gallese and may have married there, returning to Rome later.

2. Lee 1985, p. 55, n° 2160

The prostitutes of Rome in 1549

The material wealth of Rome started rising noticeably at the start of the sixteenth century, together with prostitution. In 1520 pope Leo X complained of 'licentious women who lead an ignoble and sordid life in the city we love, whose number (alas!) is increasing day by day due to the depravity of the times we live in...'.³ The Church, however, could not overlook the fact that some of these licentious women made money. Those thought worth subjecting to occasional taxation were the courtesans (*cortigiane*). The 1549 tax roll gives their location, the assessed rents for their premises, and the tax due.⁴ This tax was not annual; it was quite exceptional, in this case intended for the repair of the bridge over the Tiber called the *Ponte Santa Maria*, the remains of which are now known as the *Ponte Rotto*. The assessed rents that the courtesans paid are summarized in Fig. 1, from which it appears that Julia's, at 40 scudi, was significantly higher than that paid by most of her colleagues. The tax she had to pay was 10% of the rental, i.e. 4 scudi. The total tax paid by the 437 courtesans listed in the tax roll was 979 scudi.⁵ In addition Julia would have had to pay an annual tax of 1 scudo due from all prostitutes.⁶

3. Mendoza 2016, p. 280

4. Mendoza 2016

5. Mendoza 2016, p. 81

6. Mendoza 2016, pp. 185 et seq.

A distribution map shows the courtesans to be highly concentrated in a small part of the city, near but not adjacent to the Vatican (Fig. 2). A cluster in the south-east part of the map area marks a group of 13 courtesans round the Palazzo Colonna, close to Piazza Venezia. Those near the Ponte Sisto were also close to the Palazzo Farnese. The location of the courtesans evidently reflects the wealth and availability of clients.

Common prostitutes (*meretrici*) at this time were distributed throughout the whole of the city. To get an idea of how many there might have been we have to go back to the 1527 census of the city.¹ *Meretrici* are not listed as such, and there were only 29 courtesans – a quite improbable number. However, a way of estimating the total number of prostitutes is to count the households in which women without a stated occupation appear as the head. These women were not servants, for in that case they would almost certainly have been living in the house of their employer. Nor were they widows, for only noblewomen would have had the means to rent or own a house. In 1527 there were 2015 such households out of a total of 9285 in Rome, i.e. 22%.² The percentage of ‘female’ households depended greatly on the *riione*, or quarter. In Borgo, next to the Vatican, it was 29%, whereas in the relatively poor quarter of Trastevere it was only 11%.

1. Lee 1985

2. Delumeau 1957, vol. 2, p. 420

Making the daring assumption that the population of Rome in 1527 and 1549 was similar in all respects, we may conclude that the 2000 prostitutes of all kinds included about 400 courtesans.

The above classification of prostitutes into ‘*cortigiane*’ and ‘*meretrici*’ may seem simplistic, but follows Burchard who, in 1498, used this terminology when he wrote of *cortegiana, hoc est meretrix honesta*.³ The term ‘honest’ here seems oddly inappropriate but means simply that the courtesans had no need to resort to trickery to make a living.

3. Burchard 1884, vol. 2, pp. 442–443

Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino de Vinaya

Immediately Julia became a courtesan in 1544 a man appeared, some 20 years her senior, destined to radically change her life. He described himself in his testament as the ‘most reverend Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino de Vinaya, knight of the Order of San Pietro’, canon in Santa Maria Maggiore.⁴ Giovanni Francesco was born about 1505 in Pisa, and died about 1574.

4. SMA 1.14; and GERADUS 1569

As a member of a noble Genoese family he represented their economic interests in Rome, including supervising construction of the Palazzo Pallavicino in Campo Marzio. As a canon in the basilica of Santa Maria Maggiore he was one of the 12 priests responsible for masses and confessions, but also for general administration of the Roman church. His principal occupation, however, was as legal representative (*procuratore*) for the immensely rich Cardinal Alessandro Farnese (1520–1589). Some of Julia’s papers have survived only because they bundled up with those of Giovanni Francesco’s, which ultimately found their way into the archive of the *Pia casa degli orfani di Santa Maria in Aquiro*.⁵

5. Kolega 2015

Giovanni Francesco was assiduous in following Julia’s affairs for the rest of her life. He was always present at the drafting of contracts and often handled money on her behalf. From Julia’s point of view this was fortunate, for she would have potentially handled large sums of money, but with little idea about what to do with it. Without assistance Julia would have been easily fleeced. Near the end of her life she nominated Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino executor of her testament.⁶

6. BARGINUS 1563

Fig. 1. Histogram showing the distribution of rentals paid by 386 Roman courtesans in 1549, based on the tax roll of that year (Mendoza 2016, pp. 229–261). The histogram shows that the class interval between 10 and 20 scudi contained more courtesans than any other. The total number of courtesans in the tax roll is 437, but for many of them no rent is specified.

Fig. 2. Map showing the distribution of Roman courtesans in 1549, based on the tax list of that year. Each black symbol represents ten individuals. The river Tiber is tinted grey. Two localities where Julia da Gallesse is known to have lived are shown, namely near Piazza di Spagna (PS) and l'Ortaccio (OR). The greatest concentration of courtesans is in *rione* Campo Marzio, centred on Sant' Agostino. The outlier in the south-east part of the map indicates courtesans around Palazzo Colonna, in *rione* Trevi. The only two bridges across the Tiber in the map area at that time were the Ponte Sisto and the Ponte Sant' Angelo.

A courtesan

Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino's presence is first manifest in September 1544, the year of Julia's foray into prostitution. A contract records a loan of 50 scudi to Julia, aged 15 years.¹

1. SMA 26.129r

Sia noto a chi legera la presente come M^a Julia de galese figlia di M^a franc^a si chiama debitrice di M^s franc^o Pallavicino di scudi cinquanta di Julii x per scudo quali li ha prestato per il passato in piu volte amichevolmente li quale rinuntiando ad ogni exeptione 13 di numero haverli havuti con la speranza di haverli [Julia] promette per pagarli in questo modo cioe dieci scudi il mese cominzando dal presente mese di octobre prossimo a verun insino ala finale satisfatione. Et a fede del vero m' ha fatto fare detta M^a Julia et M^s franc^o questa poliza a me Gonz^e albero questo di 18 di 7bre 1544.

The reader should note that Madama Julia de Galese, daughter of Madama Francesca, declares herself to be in debt to Messer Francesco Pallavicino to the extent of fifty scudi of 10 juli each, which he willingly lent her in 13 instalments, hoping to have them [Julia] promises to repay the money at the rate of 10 scudi per month, starting from next October. In truth, the above text was dictated to me, Gonzales Albero, by Madama Julia and Messer Francesco, on the 18th of September 1544.

The 50 scudi had been advanced in instalments, doubtless to finance the cost of renting a house or apartment, and purchasing its furnishings. The first instalment of the scheduled repayments was made only a few days after the contract was signed, and the last instalment in April the following year. Julia was earning money, lots of it. The same year, she started keeping accounts of money spent and received, some of which have survived. The observation that Julia was keeping accounts has to be qualified, in that entries in her account books were actually written by men, who in the case of contracts like the one above were commissioned to do it, and named. The only certain example of Julia's handwriting is shown in Fig. 3. It should be said that the mere fact that she could write at all is remarkable, for most of Rome's inhabitants at this time were illiterate.

Julia's account book shows that between September 1545 and September 1546 she had an income of 130 scudi from clients.² Her income subsequently fell. In 1549 it was only 80 scudi,³ and in 1551, 85 scudi.⁴ The money was always delivered by the client who would write in the account book that the money had been paid and sign it. Occasionally the money was delivered by an intermediary.

2. SMA 152.54r

3. SMA 26.136v

4. SMA 26.141r

Clients were charged either 10 scudi or 11 scudi for a visit – the standard rate for courtesans in Rome at this time.⁵ It may be presumed that a payment of 11 scudi indicates that clients stayed to dinner. It must be said that the motive of these very expensive visits was not primarily sexual. The clients found not only a luxurious environment, but a woman always sympathetic to their problems, fantasies, hopes and despairs, the object being to induce their return. Julia succeeded. A certain Giovanni Francesco Migliorelli returned to her five times in the year 1549 alone.

5. Delumeau 1957, vol. 2, p. 417

There is no evidence in Julia's cash accounts indicating that she had more than one client at a time, except, perhaps, in the inventory of the dining-room furniture of the house

in which she died. Among other items this records three chairs upholstered with gilded leather (*sedie di corame vecchie*), one of which was ‘for a woman’.¹

1. BARGINUS 1565,
f. 180r

It can be seen from the personal papers of the celebrated courtesan Isabella de Luna, which are also in the archive of the *Pia Casa*, that she charged her clients the same as Julia, even though she was much better known. But there are two notable differences. Firstly, Isabella’s income was much greater. In 1547 she earned 300 scudi. Secondly, her income came mainly in multiples of 11, showing that she entertained groups of men (and perhaps women) to dinner. For example, in the year 1547 nine clients paid 11 scudi, but another seven came in groups of two, three, or on one occasion, five.²

2. SMA 26.132r

In September 1554, Julia appeared in an official document as a *curialis* for the last time.³ She had sufficient rents deriving from her houses, roughly 100 scudi per year, to live in comfort in her own house and devote herself to Marzio, her newly born son. Her retirement doubtless attracted notice, especially among her former clients, some of whom approached her for loans.

3. VALERIUS 1554

The houses in Piazza di Monte d’Oro

By 1551 Julia had saved enough money to buy her first house, next to the Piazza di Monte d’Oro.⁴ Prior to 1494 this area of Rome had been a vegetable garden (*orto*), hence its name l’Ortaccio.⁵ From Falda’s perspective view of Rome published in 1676 we see that the houses in the Piazza di Monte d’Oro were terraced, two or three stories high, with chimneys, and had back gardens. An estimate Julia requested for renovations to the house, dated 2 July 1551, is entitled ‘Misura et estima de lavori de muro de manufatura quali affati fare madonna julia da Galesio in una sua casa posta in Campo martio...’⁶ This estimate, on 25 closely written pages, reveals that the house, though only 50 years old, was practically a ruin. The total cost of the repairs was estimated at 307 scudi. Further repairs over the years 1555 to 1563 totalled another 726 scudi, though some of this may have been for other houses Julia had bought in the meantime, and which are mentioned in her testament.

4. SMA 152.112r

5. Gnoli 1939,
pp. 194-195

6. SMA 152.1r-7r

The estimate for repairs reveals a typical townhouse of the period, on three floors, together with two cellars. There were ten rooms and a kitchen. Several rooms had fireplaces and above the roof towered seven chimney stacks, all of which had to be rebuilt. The floors of the house (excluding the cellars and kitchen), which were relaid with new terracotta tiles, covered 290 square metres.⁷ The new windows are not described as glazed, so they probably had translucent waxed paper panes guarded by wooden shutters. The frontage of the house onto the public road was 10 m, while at the back of the house there was a loggia facing onto a garden. The wooden stairs to the first and second floors were 1.3 m wide, giving ample room for two people, walking side by side. The rubble resulting from the work on the house was thrown into the muddy road outside.⁸ Altogether the house appears to have been originally intended for a family of the merchant class, but evidently not big enough for Julia. In 1552 she commissioned an extension by making use of the

7. SMA 152.2v:
6000 square palmi.

8. SMA 152.6v

the garden at the rear:¹

1. SMA 152.117r

The reception room (*sala*) and one other room in the house had their newly plastered walls covered by panels of gilded leather (*corami*), a beautiful and very expensive material which in later centuries was substituted by wallpaper. Even one of these panels would have gone a long way to embellish a room, but Julia bought many. Panels costing 94 scudi were ordered from Giovanni Rusconi in July 1546,² and still more in 1552 from the same craftsman costing 35 scudi.³ Giovanni Rusconi was a well-known Roman leather gilder (*auripellario*) who worked near Santa Lucia in Via dei Banchi Vecchi.⁴ Other wealthy courtesans doubtless had panels of gilded leather; Tullia d'Aragona had ten of them.⁵ They also adorned the rooms of noble houses, for example the Palazzo Chigi in Ariccia.⁶ Some seventeenth century Dutch paintings of interiors by Jan Vermeer and Pieter de Hooch show interiors with gilded leather panels completely covering the walls.

2. SMA 152.57r

3. SMA 152.75r

4. Bertolotti 1884,
pp. 66, 136, 138

5. ROMAULIS 1556b,
f. 80v

6. Rodolfo & Volpi
2014

In November 1550 Julia also bought 152 tapestry panels (*pani de ratza*) from Filippo Brando costing 103 scudi.⁷

7. SMA 26.141r

The elaborate furnishings of Julia's house, intended to suit the tastes of her wealthy clientele, did not come close to those of the famous Roman courtesan Imperia Cognati (†1512), if we can believe the description given by the nobleman Angelo del Bufalo to Matteo Bandello, the novelist.⁸ One may doubt, however, that the courtesans paying rents of less than 20 scudi per year, who were in the majority, would have been able to afford such luxury.

8. Bandello 1554,
novella XLII

It appears from the inventory of Julia's possessions compiled after her death in 1565 that she had left the house described above, probably in 1555, and died in a smaller house next door.⁹ This also belonged to her. The inventory shows that it had six rooms on three floors, including a basement kitchen. It was one of the two houses Julia bequeathed to the Hospital of San Giacomo. When the Catasto Gregoriano was formed in 1824 the Hospital still owned one of these properties, at n° 89 and 90 Via dell'Arancio,¹⁰ but Julia died next door, at n° 91, on the corner of Piazza di Monte d'Oro (*angulum versus plateam*).¹¹ All Julia's possessions were in this house, but any carpets, tapestries or gilded leather panels once present in the main house (*casa magna*) are missing, probably because they had been sold. That house could then have been let unfurnished.

9. BARGINUS 1565

10. Campomarzio
Plate III, part. 382

11. BARGINUS 1565,
f. 179r

Armenia Mentebuona

Part of one of Julia's houses in l'Ortaccio was rented to a courtesan called Armenia Mentebuona, who was evidently such a nuisance to Julia and her tenants that in 1562 she raised a case against her before the curia, claiming damages of 500 scudi.¹² Armenia appears in the document as a *curiale*, i.e. a courtesan, whereas Julia, no longer a courtesan, is a *domina*, i.e. a respectable woman. A courtesan in the 1549 tax roll called Lucrezia Mentebuona, working from a house very near the Piazza di Monte d'Oro, may have been Lucrezia's mother.

12. SMA 152.44r

The Mentebuona, or Mentebona, were a notable Roman family, with their burial place in Santa Maria sopra Minerva.¹

1. Forcella 1869, vol. 1, n° 1780

Julia's clients

The most striking thing about Julia's clients was their rarity. Her cash account books show that there was, on average, about one in six weeks, giving her ample time to display herself in public, and charm the company in private. If the Giovanni Francesco Migliorelli mentioned earlier is indicative Julia would have only needed a clientele of two or three men to reach her income of around 100 scudi per year. Another occupation for Julia would have been writing letters to clients.² Letter writing served to sustain the attachment between client and courtesan, as it may between a husband and wife.

2. Masson 1975, pp. 61–66; Ferrai 1884

Julia wrote a volume of recollections entitled 'Memorie diverse notate da Giulia (Tagliacozzi) da Gallese dell'anno 1555 al 1559', which once formed tome 153 in the archive of the *Pia casa*. The volume might have told us a great deal about Julia's life and her clients, but a nineteenth century archivist discarded it, along with many others, as being of no material interest to the *Pia casa degli orfani*. Consequently, most of Julia's clients are just names about whom little can be said. But there are a few which stand out. These were men who borrowed money from her, who we may legitimately suppose had once been her clients. They were Pompeo Giustini, his brother Cosimo Giustini, and Tommaso Armentieri.

In 1556 we find Julia, now aged 26 years, investing 150 scudi at 10% in a mortgage (*censo*) over a property in *rione* Parione belonging to the nobleman, Pompeo Giustini de Castello.³ She was at home when she signed the contract, with Francesco Pallavicino beside her which was just as well considering Pompeo's character. The mortgage document is of particular interest for it describes Julia as the daughter of the 'late Roberto Tagliacozzo di Gallese'. Tagliacozzo is a Jewish name, mainly found in Rome, which Julia never used except when notaries required it. She preferred to call herself Julia da Gallese.

3. ROMAULIS 1556a

Two years later, in January 1558, Julia granted an unsecured loan of 200 scudi at 12% interest to Cosimo Giustini de Castello, brother of the Pompeo just mentioned.⁴ The contract contains a surprising clause requiring the loan to be repaid in the event that Julia's son *Martio de Justinis* should die by natural causes. In 1558 Cosimo was but a young man, not long graduated in law, but already a knight of the Order of San Pietro and subsequently a priest. In later life he commissioned the building of the Palazzo Giustini in Piazza Colonna, and accumulated an extensive collection of sculptures.⁵ He was murdered in 1603, at which time he was described as *referendario utriusque Signaturae*, i.e. a judge in the court of appeal of the Roman church.

4. SMA 152.36r

5. Buccino 2011

The Giustini were a notable Roman family about which much has been written see Thomas Cohen's fascinating description of the trial of Pompeo Giustini in 1557, in which we discover that Pompeo was a brutal man who, when thwarted, was apt to use

his hand to women and his sword to men.¹ He was brought to trial accused by his elder brother Ascanio of forcing their dying sister Vittoria, aged 15 years, to leave her dowry money to Pompeo and his brothers Pietro Paolo, Cosimo and Fabrizio, but not to Ascanio and his sisters.

1. Cohen 2004, pp. 73–123

There followed a loan by Julia to Tommaso Armentieri in March 1559.² Tommaso Armentieri (†1565), was secretary and major-domo to Margherita d’Austria, daughter of the emperor Charles V and wife of Ottavio Farnese, Duca di Parma.³ Tommaso was Spanish, born in Salamanca, and, to judge from the charitable bequests he made in his testament, very wealthy. The loan document, like that of Cosimo Giustini, is for 200 scudi at 12% interest, and requires repayment on the death by natural causes of *Martio Justini*.

2. SMA 152.38r

3. Hunter 1996, p, 169

Despite their wealth these men were evidently short of cash, and had to borrow from Julia da Gallese, and perhaps others. This is not surprising, for many of the richest men in sixteenth century Rome grossly overspent their income on such things as courtesans and gambling, and ostentatious projects like majestic buildings, art collections, dowries and carriages, making up the deficit by borrowing.⁴

4. Delumeau 1957, vol. 1, p. 480

5. SMA 152.40r

Julia’s last documented loan was to Moses Rubini and his son (100 scudi) in 1562.⁵ This was a profit sharing agreement concerned with the purchase and resale of textiles. It is not suggested here that Moses was a former client of Julia. A Jewish merchant would probably have had better things to do. Significantly, this loan was called in on 18 January 1565, probably to cover the cost of Julia’s funeral a few weeks later.

Marzio

Julia’s son Marzio is first mentioned in an instrument dated 11 September 1554.⁶ That same year the last page of one of Julia’s account books is completely occupied by an elegantly written dedication to ‘Signora Julia Gallese my dearest mistress’.⁷ It reads;

6. VALERIUS 1554

7. SMA 26.153r

Signora Julia gallese padrona mia carissima

*Dum Jaga montis aper fluvios dum piscis amabit
Semper honos nomenque tuum laudesque manebunt*

The Latin verse is abbreviated from Virgil’s fifth *Ecloga*, lines 76–78. It can be translated as ‘while the boar loves the mountain top, and the fish the stream, your honour, name, and fame will forever endure’. It was clearly written by someone with a classical education, perhaps Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino.

Marzio’s mother engaged a wet-nurse for him in January of the following year, 1555.⁸ This was a woman called Giovanna, the wife of Giovanni Bertero of Castel Novo in Piedmont, who had evidently lost her child and left her husband. Giovanna remained in

8. SMA 152.82r

Julia's service for seven years. The monthly wage she received was 10 *carlini* in cash, i.e. one scudo per month, in addition to which she would have had board and lodging. Giovanna left Julia's service in May 1557;

Addi 10 de Maggio 1557

Per la presente si fa fede qualmente Giovanna piemontese serva della M^a Julia de gallesse si chiama contenta et satisfatta dalla dicta m^a Julia di tutto quello l'havesse servita tanto in dare latte al suo figliolo Martio quanto in servirla per serva per insino al dicto giorno 10 de Maggio 1557...¹

1. SMA 26.156r

10th May 1557

The Piedmontese Giovanna, servant of Madama Julia de Gallesse here declares herself to be fully content and satisfied with the treatment she has had both as wet-nurse for Madama Julia's son Marzio and as her servant, up to the present day 10 May 1557.

But, as Julia wrote in her own hand, Giovanna soon returned (Fig. 3);

Memoria come giovanna piemontese
torno a stare con me adi primo de
giugno 1557

Figure 3. The hand-writing of Julia da Gallesse, recording the return of her Piedmontese servant Giovanna on the first of June 1557; 'Memoria come giovanna piemontese torno a stare con me adi primo de giugno 1557'.²

2. SMA 26.157v.

Giovanna left Julia's service definitively in February 1562,³ and was immediately followed by Antonina, who remained with Julia till she died. Julia seems to have been well pleased by Antonina, and in her testament left her 50 scudi together with her bed, a straw mattress, bed linen, her clothes and trinkets.⁴ The 50 scudi would have been roughly four times Antonina's annual salary.

3. SMA 26.207r

4. BARGINUS 1563,
f. 176r

The annual salary of Julia's servants must have been about 20 scudi, i.e. 12 scudi in cash and 8 scudi for their accommodation. At this time the average salary of university teachers in Rome was about 300 scudi.⁵ This is 17 times greater than the wage of Julia's servants. Today this ratio would be about 4, illustrating the way that wealth in Renaissance Rome was concentrated in a tiny proportion of the population. The income of a noble Roman family at that time would have been at the very least 1000 scudi per year.

5. Renazzi 1803,
vols. 2 & 3

Marzio's father

The parentage of Marzio was disputed. His surname was first mentioned four years after he was born, in January 1558, in the loan document for Cosimo Giustini (discussed earlier). Here he is referred to as *Martij de justinis*.⁶ One might suppose from this that Marzio was thought by Cosimo to be his son. But Julia also had dealings with Cosimo's

6. SMA 152.36r

brother Pompeo Giustini, as described above, so doubt remains. In Julia's testament of September 1563 she refers to her son as *Martio Mario de Vinaia*. The surname 'de Vinaia' is very rare in Italy, but was used by Francesco Pallavicino in his testament, as mentioned earlier, and also in earlier documents. For example, *Jo: Francisco Pallavicino de Vinaia* appears in an invoice for timber supplied to Michelangelo Buonarroti in Rome in September 1540. This was while Michelangelo was working on the Sistine chapel.¹

1. Frey 1909, p. 169

Considering the frequency of encounters between courtesans and clients (say once a month) nice calculations and much discussion would have been needed to deduce who was the father of any resulting child. In Marzio's case these discussions must have continued for years. However, Julia and Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino were clearly convinced that Marzio was their child, so that he appears on Julia's gravestone as *Marzio Pallavicino*. His father's connection with the Church is in no way remarkable. It may be recalled that Cardinal Alessandro Farnese had a child, Clelia Farnese, born in 1556 only two years after Marzio. The mother of Clelia is a mystery, but the child grew into a beautiful woman, cherished by her father and much admired in Rome. Again, the eminent humanist Pietro Bembo in 1522 embraced both an oath of celibacy (as a Knight Hospitaller) and a young woman, Faustina Morosina della Torre, said to have been formerly a courtesan.² They met when she was 16 years old and had three children over the years 1523 to 1528. Bembo was nominated cardinal in 1539.

2. Dionisotti 1966

Marzio died in January 1569, aged 15 years.³ A summary of expenditure on his behalf for bespoke clothes and medical expenses covering the period June to December 1567 (Appendix 1) shows that although Marzio's mother had died two years previously, no expense was being spared on his clothes, or education. It also gives a clear idea of the cost of fine clothes at this time. Only a few days after Marzio's death his father revoked the testament of 1566 which made ample provision for Marzio,⁴ and instead bestowed his wealth on the Hospital and orphanage of San Giacomo, the convent of the *Convertite*, and the convent of Santa Caterina dei Funari.⁵

3. PAULIS 1563, f. 128v

4. BARGINUS 1566

5. GERARDUS 1569

Intimations of mortality

Julia started using large quantities of oximel and cinnamon in 1562.⁶ Oximel, a mixture of honey and vinegar, was used for masking the taste of some medicines, and also used to dress ulcers. Although only 33 years old she appears to have been told she was suffering from a potentially deadly illness. A year later, in September 1563, the notary Johannes Barginus drafted her testament in her presence and that of Giovanni Francesco.⁷ The executor of the testament, and guardian of Marzio, was named as Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino. She starts by saying that she wanted to be buried in the church of San Rocco, very near her home, together with her late mother, Francesca. The grave was to be before the image of Santa Brigida, and had to be covered with a marble ledger-stone. The saint was, of course, Santa Brigida of Sweden, who settled in Rome in 1349 and dedicated herself to the

6. SMA 152.112r

7. BARGINUS 1563

care of the poor. Julia then made bequests to various Roman institutions, totalling 205 scudi;

Chiesa di San Rocco (50 scudi),
Chiesa di San Giuseppe 'prope Marforio' i.e. San Giuseppe dei Falegnami (50 scudi)
Ospedale di San Rocco (10 scudi)
Ospedale di San Giacomo degli Incurabili (50 scudi)
Monastero della Santissima Trinità dei Monti (10 scudi),
Arciconfraternita del SS. Crocifisso in San Marcello (10 scudi),
Confraternita di Santa Maria del Pianto (10 scudi),
Monastero degli orfani e orfane di Roma, i.e. the Pia casa degli orfani (10 scudi),
Monastero di Santa Maria Maddalena delle Convertite,
Confraternita del Corpus Christi in San Lorenzo in Lucina (5 scudi)

Julia explains in her testament that these bequests had the aim of absolving her from sin (*in remissione peccati*), an essential prerequisite for eternal life. There was, however, an exception. This was the bequest to the Monastero delle Convertite. This institution was for the support of repentant prostitutes. The quota was predetermined by law at a fifth of the deceased's entire estate. It had, apparently, been paid in advance, for there is an entry in the accounts for 1563 recording an *instrumento de liberatione dalle Convertite*.¹

1. SMA 26.236r

Julia also requested that there should be a sung mass (*missa cantata*) every year on the anniversary of her death.² It was at this time common for testators to request masses to be said for the repose of their souls, but rare that they should ask for them to be sung. Sung masses, little changed from those of Julia's day, are still performed in some Roman churches. They are quite different to the requiem masses which accompany funerals.

2. BARGINUS 1565,
f. 176v

Julia's substantial bequest to the church of San Giuseppe dei Falegnami, close to the Campidoglio, may indicate that she had some connection with carpentry (*falegnameria*) because in March 1552 she had already spent 10 scudi in the restoration of the chapel of San Giuseppe in that church.³ It should be noted that in Julia's day the church of San Giuseppe was often known as San Pietro in Carcere – an ancient church rented by the carpenters guild in 1540, and later rebuilt and renamed.

3. SMA 26.188r

Julia's attachment to her family of origin is shown by several generous bequests. Flaminia, daughter of Julia's sister Giacobba, was left 150 scudi, her niece Francesca Micinelli of Gallese was left 100 scudi, while her nephew Matteo Tagliacozzo got 100 scudi.

For inheritance purposes Julia's estate devolved upon her young son Marzio, but in case he were to die without any heirs, as indeed happened, it was to be divided into two equal parts. One part was destined for her nephews and nieces and the other part to the Hospital of San Giacomo degli Incurabili.

Consequently, on Marzio's death in 1569, the main house (*casa grande*) passed to Julia's nieces and nephews, while the two smaller houses adjacent went to the Hospital of San Giacomo. It was because of this bequest to the Hospital that the suburban Roman street *Via Giulia di Gallese* was given its name in 1921.

Julia's debt to Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino

Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino insisted seven months after Julia had published her testament, and nine months before she died, that she should admit the financial help he had given her over the years.¹ The text of the memorandum is so revealing that it is here given in full, although it is far from clear why he thought it necessary;

1. SMA 152.122r

Io giulia del q. roberto di gallese confesso per la presente esser vera et legitima debitrice del mag^{co} Mr giovan francesco palauicino de conto fatto insieme de ogni spesa fatta per me tanto per conto di fabrice dele mie case fatte et spese fatte et salarij et vestire, e calzare per Martio Mio figliuolo tanto a mastro Timoteo quanto a qualsivoglia altra persona e, cosi de ogni altra cosa e denari imprestatomi e cosi quelli lui hauesse hauti da me contanti, si riserba come rescossi a mio nome sino a questo di di tutti mi chiamo quieta contenta e sadisfatta e ne li fo ampla quittance e cosi lui a me ogni volta che io li daro scudi settantatre di moneta e baiocchi quarantuno che li resto a dare sino a questo di 20 d'aprile prossimo passato quali prometto pagarneli ad ogni sua requisitione et per cautela dell una e l'altra parte habbiamo sottoscritta la presente di nostra propria mano questo di 20 d'aprile 1564.

I Julia, daughter of the late Roberto of Gallese, declare myself with this note to be the true and legitimate debtor of the magnificent Messer Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino for the money expended on my behalf, both for the restoration of my houses, for the pocket money, clothes and shoes for Marzio my son, for the salary of Master Timoteo, or any other person, and for money which he has lent me, always allowing for the sums which I have paid him, down to today. For all this I declare myself fully satisfied, and so does he [Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino] every time I pay him 73 scudi and 41 baiocchi which I owe him as of today, 20 April, and I promise to pay them at any further request, and to avoid any misunderstandings we have signed the present memorandum in our own hands this day 20th April 1564.

Master Timoteo was Marzio's tutor.² The claim that Giovanni Francesco had paid for the restoration of the dilapidated houses Julia bought overlooks the perpetual mortgage over her house (*domus magna*) in l'Ortaccio which he obliged her to grant him.³ It meant that Julia and her heirs had to pay Giovanni Francesco 20 scudi annually. It was not the first mortgage of its kind. Moreover, the very substantial sum of 73 scudi mentioned in the memorandum, which Julia was supposed to pay him, appears not to have been either the first or the last. Had she continued to pay it for, say, another five or six years, her debt to Giovanni Francesco would probably have been extinguished.

2. SMA 26.236v

3. VALERIUS 1554

The memorandum above seems to represent an effort by Giovanni Francesco to show that the relationship between him and Julia was not exploitative on his part, or on hers.

The end

The exact date of Julia's death is not recorded, but must have been about 1 February 1565, three days before the burial. The room she died in can be partially reconstructed from the inventory of her possessions compiled on 4 February, a few days after her death.⁴

4. BARGINUS 1565,
ff. 181v–182v

Julia slept in a four-poster bed (*padiglione*) with a bolster, silk covered pillows, sheets, three woollen blankets and a linen bed cover. The bed frame was high enough to keep

beneath it a truckle-bed, which could have been pulled out and used by Julia's maid Antonina at night. Antonina would have kept the fire bright (this was the coldest winter of the century) and attended to her mistress's needs. The bedroom had, among other things, a *prie-dieu* with an image of the Madonna in front of it, a walnut writing desk with drawers and two ink pots, a harpsichord, five attractively bound prayer-books, a large mirror (later valued at 4 scudi), a little table 'to eat in front of the fire', three chests of drawers and two silver chandeliers. No books, music scores or carpets are mentioned anywhere in the house, but there were four pictures. Two were in the bedroom, one of Santa Caterina and the other described as being *de fantasia*. Julia also kept her valuables there, including the cash which she entrusted to Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino just before she died. The amount is not recorded, but he told the notary that he still had 210 scudi in hand.¹

1. BARGINUS 1565,
f. 183r

Few of the beautiful clothes Julia must once have had appear in the inventory. Indeed, in her bedroom there are only petticoats and dressing gowns. The only two dresses she might have gone out in were in store, giving the impression that she was house-bound. All that remained of the halcyon years were two beautiful hats;²

2. BARGINUS 1565,
f. 179v

un capello de paglia sottile fodrato di tafetta sottile con suo cordone di seta turchina et d'oro [e] una berreta di veluto negro con un cordone di velo con una trinetta d'oro attorno

a hat made of fine straw, with a fine silken lining and a hatband of deep blue silk with gold threads [and] a beret of black velvet, the veil trimmed with gold lace

Julia's assets

The inventory of Julia's possessions compiled a few days after she died provides details of all her possessions, though without stating their value.³ However, a few items were subsequently valued by dealers whose estimates are shown in Appendix 2. The value of the loans Julia made is stated in the relevant contracts. She also spent about 1000 scudi in restoring her houses. From these and other sources a fairly reliable figure for the total value of Julia's assets can be roughly estimated, in scudi, as follows;

3. BARGINUS 1565

Cash and redeemable loans.....	800
Houses.....	1800
Furniture and other moveables.....	400
	<hr/>
Total.....	3000

It is impossible that Julia could have accumulated 3000 scudi in only 10 years as a courtesan, earning, as she did, no more than 100 scudi a year. She could have saved enough from her earnings to buy dilapidated houses, to accumulate the cash for the loans, and perhaps also the furnishings of her houses, but no more. Giovanni Francesco's contribution to the restoration of her houses was substantial, and Julia did not live long enough to repay it.

The Grave of Julia da Gallese

Julia wrote in her testament that she wanted to be buried in the church of San Rocco. Vincenzo Forcella, who must have seen the stone about 1875, records that it was in front of the third chapel on the right as one enters the church, and remarks that it was adorned by a life-sized engraved figure of a woman in a long dress, alluding to Julia.¹ Neither this gravestone, nor any of the others once set into the floor of the church, survived nineteenth century restorations. The inscription is dated 4 February 1565. This was probably the day Julia was buried, for Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino the day before bought clothes for her funeral. The epitaph below is that recorded by Gaspare Alveri in the seventeenth century, when the stone was still little worn and the inscription legible;²

1. Forcella 1876, vol. 7, n° 918

2. Alveri 1664, p. 68

JULIÆ ROBERTI FILIÆ TAGLIACOSSIÆ DOMO
GALLESIO EX SABINIS MATRI OPTIMÆ
QUÆVIX. ANNOS XXXV.
ꝛ
FRANCISCÆ AVIÆ MATERNÆ PIENTISSIMÆ
VIX ANN. LX.
MARCIVS PALLAVICINUS POSUIT IV.
NON. FEBRAURIJ
MDLXV

This stone was placed here by Marzio Pallavicino on 4 February 1565 for Julia Tagliacozzo, daughter of Roberto, native of Gallese in Sabina, his excellent mother, who lived for 35 years, and for Francesca, his most pious grandmother, who lived for 60 years

The stone purports to have been provided by Julia's son Marzio, but he was only 11 years old at the time. It must have been his father who had arranged it and decided to make public his paternity of Marzio. All that Marzio could have done was to watch his mother being lowered into her grave, and let the tears run down his face.

Julia da Gallese; a typical Roman courtesan?

Julia da Gallese never fell into debt, never fell foul of the law, and never wrote anything that has survived. She died apparently unknown to contemporary commentators. She had, however, evolved over 20 years from an almost penniless girl into a wealthy woman, living in retirement in her own comfortably furnished house, with an annual income of some 200 scudi from rents and investments. Can she be taken as typical of the 400 odd courtesans of sixteenth century Rome?

Julia was fortunate indeed to have been guided by Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino who was, among other things, an experienced businessman. To see his influence it is sufficient to compare the loan contract of September 1544, when she started her career

aged 15 years, with the memorandum she underwrote in April 1564, only months before she died, which attests to the financial help she had had from Giovanni Francesco. Both documents reveal the firm, not to say iron hand, of Giovanni Francesco.

Why Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino should have spent so much time and money serving Julia's interests invites speculation. Alexandra Kolega has claimed that he had been delegated by Cardinal Farnese to act as legal tutor to the courtesans Julia da Gallese and Isabella de Luna.¹ She does not, however, cite any documentary evidence of any such instructions. As for the claim that Giovanni Francesco acted for Isabella de Luna, there is practically no evidence apart from the fact that he inherited her personal archive. The executors of Isabella's testament were Don Fernando de Torres and Ascanio Celso di Nepi. Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino was not the administrator (*curatore*) of her estate as stated by Kolega.² He appears in the schedule of expenses regarding the administration of her estate *post mortem*, but not as the administrator.³

1. Kolega 2015, pp. 48 & 77

2. Kolega 2015, p. 50
3. SMA 26.173r

Another possible reason for Giovanni Francesco's interest in Julia is that he was privy to Julia's intended career through her mother, Francesca, and decided to make her his sugar baby, or concubine. More crudely, Julia was to be financially supported by Giovanni Francesco in return for the promise of sexual favours, as has already suggested by Alessandra Camerano.⁴ However, Julia had many clients, not just one. And the memorandum of understanding underwritten by Julia and Giovanni Francesco in 1564 makes clear that the relationship between them was not parasitic.

4. Camerano 2022, p. 96

It may be noted that some courtesans would willingly become temporary concubines if it was financially advantageous, for example Isabella de Luna.⁵ The relationship between men and *meretrici* was different again; of those in the 1527 census of the parish of Sant' Andrea Nazareno (Via Giulia), a half were living with an *amico*. i.e. a male 'friend'.⁶ In this case it was the men who were financially advantaged rather than the women.

5. Lanciani 1903, p. 84

6. Mantoni 2016, p. 216

A kinder motive for the bond between Julia and Giovanni Francesco is that, however they met, they came to love each other. This would better explain his willingness to help her, and the quite remarkable fact that she abandoned her profession at the age of 26 years in order to dedicate her life to her newly born son Marzio. It would also explain his never failing presence beside her, to the very end.

The link between Giovanni Francesco, Julia and her mother may have been indirect, in that they were members of the household of Cardinal Farnese. The households of cardinals were very large. In the 1527 census of Rome almost 5% of the total population of the city were dependants of cardinals and the pope. The Farnese household then included more than 300 persons (*bocche*). The Alidosi family, into which Julia may briefly have married, and Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino were members of this 'family'. It is even possible that Giovanni Francesco had known Julia since she was born.

Without the guidance of Giovanni Francesco Pallavicino, Julia might well have ended her days in poverty like Tullia d'Aragona (†1556), celebrated for her poetry,⁷ but

7. Hairston 2014

unfortunate in having had no valid financial advice, even if the nobleman Paolo Emilio Orsini (†1554), feudal lord of Monterotondo claimed to be her protector.¹ Tullia worked near the Piazza di Campo Marzio in 1549, but eventually retreated to an inn in Trastevere to die. The inventory of the personal effects and furniture which she took with her valued them at 232 scudi, including 43 scudi in cash.² Most of her jewels had been pawned to Antonio Trivulzio, Bishop of Toulon, for 45 scudi. No debts, credits or buildings are listed in the inventory, but nevertheless Tullia hoped that what she left would suffice to maintain and educate her young son, Celio.

1. Biagi 1897, p. 96

2. ROMAULIS 1556b
f. 81v

On the other hand, Julia's wealth did not come near to that of her contemporary, the celebrated Isabella de Luna, who was at least 10 years her senior. As already noted, Isabella's income was three times that of Julia and the investments she made were correspondingly larger. For instance, in August 1560 Isabella made a one year loan of 1000 scudi, secured over land near Naples, to Giovanni Domenico Sorrentino, abbot of San Giovanni Maggiore in Naples.³ The size of this loan exceeded the total tax levied on the courtesans of Rome in 1549. But it was not enough for Giovanni Domenico. In December of the same year Isabella made him another loan, secured over land, this time 700 scudi, also repayable in a year.⁴ These loans together equate to 255 000 euros worth of gold, making Isabella seem more a banker than a courtesan.

3. SMA 26.10r

4. SMA 26.12r

In summary, it seems that Julia might, indeed, be representative of the more successful Roman courtesans. If the rent she was assessed on (40 scudi annually) is indicative, she was, as already noted, far above the average paid by courtesans in 1549, along with Tullia d'Aragona (40 scudi) and Isabella de Luna (100 scudi). Julia made the money she hoped for; had a devoted man at her side, and had a child which survived her. Her early death was not unusual for the sixteenth century. The thing she still wished, as her lost volume of memoirs shows, was to be remembered.

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Appendix 1. Expenses of Marzio Pallavicino from June to December 1567

Adi 26 de Giugno 1567, Conto di diverse spese per Martio

E prima per Gio. Batt. ponte toscano per palmi 13 $\frac{1}{2}$ di taffetta negro per calze e gipone a prezzo di 22 il palmo.....	14 18 0
E piu, a di detto per il mede[si]mo Gio. Batt. per palmi 30 $\frac{1}{2}$ de giambelotto per una veste per casa a prezzo 8 il palmo.....	12 4 0
E piu, a di detto e fu prima in dui volte per v 2 doro dati per hippolito al mastro de scrivere.....	8 0 0
E piu, a di detto e fu prima per v uno doro dato per salvagina al medico quando fu indisposto.....	4 0 0
E piu a di detto e fu prima per palmi 2 di veluto negro per una Beretta pagati da detta salvagina.....	4 5 0
E piu per palmi 5 di tela per uno Gibone pagati per la detta.....	1 18 6
E piu per scarpe pianelle, e datoli de contanti per la detta salvagina.....	2 18 0
E piu a di 9 de agosto per fodre havute da sebastiano zenochio regatiero pagati per la detta.....	2 10 0
E piu a di 10 de ottobre per v 5 doro dati al medico che lo ha curato in la sua infirmita, dati da salvagina.....	20 0 0
E piu a di 27 di novembre per una beretto di panno.....	1 7 0
E piu a di ultimo di dicembre per sebastiano danone regatiero per tele fustanio, e altre cose, come per il conto dato.....	2 14 0
E piu per fare disignare dui giponi.....	1 0 0
E piu a di ultimo di dicembre per nicolo petule per quanto sono importate le medicine e siloppi [sciroppi] havuti in la infirmita del detto martio.....	18 6 0
E piu a di detto per Jeronimo bozio Calzolaro per quanto ha importato il conto di detto martio de calze e calzette, e altre cose havuto da la sua botega.....	37 8 4
E piu a di detto per mastro Gasparo sartore per quanto importa il conto delle manifatture.....	9 10 6
E piu a di detto per Gio. Batta. mercante toscano per quanto si e saldato il conto del detto martio delli velluti, rasi, e taffeta havuti.....	40 0 0
E piu per quanto importa il suo conto del Calegaro per scarpe, e stivalette....	9 16 0
Spese per fattione de una berretta di veluto da ambrosio milanese.....	1 2 0
	<hr/>
	195 2 0

Values are in scudi. The data comes from SMA 152.140r.

Appendix 2. Value of certain items formerly belonging to
Julia da Gallese

Lista delle robbe della sig^{ra} Giulia de galesio
estimate per li Infrascritti

Cento sessanta pelle d'oro con i frisi a b ⁱ 18 la pelle...	v 28
Cinq[e] canne e mezza de raso verde fiorentino a v quattro di moneta la canna.....	v 22
Un paro de calze bianche con taffeta bianco.....	v 1/80
Un panno de spalle.....	v 2
Una medaglia doro et una corona de granate et oro....	v 24
Un spechio di cristallo.....	v 4
Un paro di lensuoli novi.....	v 4
Un paro de calzette di setta bianca.....	v 2
Doi camise lavorate doro e di setta.....	v 3
	<hr/>
	90/80

Values are in scudi and baiocchi. The valuers were Giovanni Antonio de Pesaro and Bernardo Sensolo. The text is from SMA 26.39r.

